

EVALUATION OF AQUIFER POTENTIAL AND TRANSMISSIVITY USING Dar – Zarrouk PARAMETERS IN NANDO AND ITS ENVIRONS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15106753>

Abstract

Groundwater presents itself as a viable and safe source of potable water and a widely accepted and better alternative to surface water resources. It contributes substantially to the water needs for most domestic, municipal and industrial purposes worldwide, due to its availability in almost all parts of the world. This research is aimed at evaluating the groundwater potential and transmissivity capacity of the aquifer unit at Nando, Aguleri and Igbariam. This study identifies areas with good groundwater potential and the aquifer transmissibility of the study area and hence will give the populace idea on the actual depth and water flow rate where good water table can be harnessed. A geophysical survey using electrical resistivity method was conducted at Nando, Aguleri and Igbariam in Anambra East L.G.A of Anambra State, Nigeria. The study areas lies within longitudes 6°51'35.0"E - 6°57'07.5"E and latitudes 6°17'14.2"N - 6°23'50.3"N. Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) was carried out with a digital read out resistivity meter (ABEM SAS 1000). The VES data interpretations were done using INTERPEX software and the VES results. The lithology was inferred to the layers by correlating the lithology log of one of the boreholes drilled in the study area and the geology of the study area. The VES result shows four 4 – 6 lithologic layers with the subsurface sequence varying as follows: Dry sand, Shale, Water saturated sand, Sand, Shaly sand, Silty shale, Red earth and Sandstone. The Water saturated sand layers constituted the aquifer unit in the area and its thickness of 20 m and 53.33 m. The aquifer transmissivity was determined by calculating for hydraulic conductivity and multiplying with the thickness of the aquifer layer. The aquifer transmissivity value obtained for VES 1 and 2 are 2816.80 and 0.0438 m²/day which indicates a very good and poor aquifer transmissivity respectively. Groundwater potential zones were determined based on transmissivity values and classified the area into very good, good, moderately good, low/fairly good and poor aquifer transmissivity. We recommend that more geophysical surveys be conducted at Aguleri and Igbariam villages in other to ascertain areas where good groundwater potential could be harnessed.

Keywords: Aquifer, Vertical Electrical Sounding, transmissivity, Nando and Igbariam

INTRODUCTION

Groundwater is water beneath the earth's surface in pores and fractures of soil and rocks. Groundwater is the second largest freshwater reservoir in the world, accounting for 12% of world's freshwater reserve, the largest resource being ice-locked water (87%), while surface water accounts for just around 1% of the world's freshwater reserves (Gleick, 2011).

Groundwater, under most conditions, is safer and more reliable for use than surface water. Part of the reason for this is that surface water is more readily exposed to pollutants from factories than groundwater. This by no means says that groundwater is invulnerable to contamination. Geologically, in the basement terrain, groundwater is believed to occur within the overlying unconsolidated material derived from in-situ weathering of rocks and perhaps the fractured/faulted bedrock while in the sedimentary terrain, it is accumulated within the porous and permeable layer of the saturated zone in the subsurface (Clark, 1985; Jones, 1985; Bala and Ike, 2001). Although water is a renewable resource, its supply in suitable quality is steadily decreasing due to poor groundwater management and effect of poor waste water management, especially in developing countries like Nigeria. Moreover, the demand for this resource has increased significantly throughout the world due to population growth, socio-economic development, technological and climatic changes (Olayinka *et al.* 1999; Alcamo, 2007). The source of groundwater most times could be linked to surface run-off and infiltration of rainwater into the subsurface and streams from which it leads to the establishment of the water table and serve as a primary supplier of streams, springs lakes, bays and oceans. The textural arrangement (uniformly or tightly arranged texture, loosely arranged texture) found within most geological formations and rocks have a strong role to play in water retention and storage capacity of any rock or geological formation. Rocks/Geological formation with uniformly or tightly arranged texture have high water retaining ability (porosity) but less transmitting or mobility ability (permeability) while those with higher porosity and higher permeability have sufficiently enough to yield significant quantities of groundwater to wells and springs as such any geological formation with such characteristic is been referred to as an Aquifer. According to geological terms an Aquifer could be referred to as a body of saturated rock or geological formation through which water can easily move (permeability) into wells and streams. It can also be defined as an underground layer of water-bearing permeable rock (Olisah *et al.* 2023). The top of the water level in an aquifer is called the water table. An aquifer fills with water from rain or melted snow that drains into the ground. In certain areas, water could pass through the soil of the aquifer while in other areas it enters through joints and cracks in rocks where it moves downwards until it encounters rocks that are less permeable. Aquifers generally are known to serve as reservoirs and could dry up when people drain them faster than they are been refilled by nature. Aquifers must not only be permeable but must also be porous and are found to include rock types such as sandstones, conglomerates, fractured limestone and unconsolidated sand, gravels and fractured volcanic rocks (columnar basalts). While some aquifers have high porosity and low permeability others have high porosity and high productivity. Those with high porosity and low permeability are referred to as poor aquifers and include rocks or geological formation such as granites and schist while those with high porosity and high permeability are regarded as excellent aquifers and include rocks like fractured volcanic rocks. Aquifers are generally classed into two main categories namely confined aquifer and unconfined aquifers.

Confined Aquifers are those bodies of water found accumulating in a permeable rock and are been enclosed by two impermeable rock layers or rock bodies. Confined Aquifers are aquifers that

are found to be overlain by a confining rock layer or rock bodies, often made up of clay which might offer some form of protection from surface contamination. The geological barriers which are non-permeable and found exist between the aquifer causes the water within it to be under pressure which is comparatively more than the atmospheric pressure. Groundwater flow through aquifers is either vertically or horizontally at rates often influenced by gravity and geological formations in these areas.

Unconfined Aquifer unlike confined aquifers are generally found located near the land surface and have no layers of clay (or other impermeable geologic material) above the water table although they are found lying relatively above impermeable clay rock layers. The uppermost boundary of groundwater within the unconfined aquifer is the water table, the groundwater in an unconfined aquifer is more vulnerable to contamination from surface pollution as compared to that in confined aquifers this been so due to easy groundwater infiltration by land pollutants. Fluctuation in the level of groundwater varies and depends on the stored up groundwater in the space of the aquifer which in turn affects the rise or fall of water levels in wells that derive their source from aquifers. As groundwater becomes more important as a source of uncontaminated water, improved hydrogeological knowledge, new groundwater exploration technologies and data processing methods must be efficient to facilitate investigations and evaluation of groundwater resources.

Aquifer Transmissivity simply could be defined as the property of aquifer to transmit water. It could also be defined as the amount of water that can be transmitted horizontally through an aquifer unit by full saturated thickness of the aquifer under a hydraulic gradient of 1 or as the rate at which water of prevailing kinematic viscosity is transmitted through a unit width of aquifer under a unit gradient.

Many investigation techniques are commonly employed with the aim of estimating the spatial distribution of aquifer parameters such as hydraulic conductivity, transmissivity and aquifer depth. Unfortunately, the conventional methods for the determination of hydraulic parameters such as pumping tests, parameter measurements and grain size analysis are invasive, relatively expensive and either integrate over a largest volume of data or provide information only to a small section of the aquifer in the vicinity of the borehole. According interpolating aquifer properties between boreholes is often difficult with little or no data in which to base these extrapolations. Therefore, in areas with few pumping test information, the spatial distribution of aquifer properties cannot be confidently calculated. The application of surface resistivity method however, can provide useful method for obtaining information on aquifer properties in areas where pumping test data are sparse and subsurface conditions area appropriate. Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) techniques are a useful tool routinely used under a variety of field conditions and geological settings in hydrogeology, environmental geology and geotechnical engineering. Hence VES has proved to be effective in solving groundwater problems in most places in Nigeria (Ezeh and Ugwu 2010; Ugwu and Ezeh, 2012; Nzemeka *et al.*, 2023). Geophysicists have realized that the integration of aquifer parameters calculated from existing borehole locations and subsurface resistivity parameters extracted from resistivity measurements can be highly effective, since a correlation between hydraulic and electrical aquifer properties can be possible as both properties are related to the pore space structure and heterogeneity. For this purpose transformation of the aquifer resistivity distribution in terms of the aquifer Dar – Zarrouk parameters requires the application of physically consequential relation derived either theoretically or empirically.

The purpose of this study is to gain a better understanding of the quantity and quality of groundwater resources in the study area including over-exploitation and degradation. The results

of this study will inform groundwater management policies and provide a basis for ensuring the sustainable use of these valuable resources in the future. This study will also identify areas with good groundwater potential and the aquifer transmissibility of the study area and hence will give the populace idea on the actual depth and water flow rate where good water table can be harnessed.

1.1.1 LOCATION AND ACCESSIBILITY OF STUDY AREA

Nando, Aguleri and Igbariam are medium-sized towns, located within the Anambra valley in Anambra State, southeastern region of Nigeria with Latitude: 06°17'N - 06°20'N and Longitude: 006°51'E - 006°54'E and can be accessed through the Enugu – Onitsha Expressway by Awkuzu and Igbariam junctions respectively. Nando is bordered by the following towns and villages: Aguleri, Umueri, Anam, Anaku, Awkuzu, Omor, Ifite Ogwari, Igbariam, Igbakwu, Nteje, Nsugbe, Achalla, Umunya and Umueje (Fig 1).

Fig 1. Google map of Anambra State showing the Location of the study areas (www.google.com)

1.1.2 Statement of the Problem

The inhabitants of Nando, Aguleri and Igbariam has been experiencing difficulties in accessing groundwater as only one functional borehole sponsored by UNICEF/European Union groundwater development projects was drilled in the study area and few hand dug well owned by some individuals at their various homes. Majority of the residents go as far as Omambala river and Chukwuemeka Odimegwu Ojukwu University to fetch water for their domestic and agricultural use. The distance between Igbariam to Nando is 16km, Nando to Aguleri is about 3.6km. The growing population of the community and the increasing demand of water for their domestic use and agricultural purposes has given rise to the urgent need to address the issue of aquifer

transmissivity in Nando, Aguleri and Igbariam. For this reason, it would be very helpful to explore the geological formations of the aquifer units of Nando, Aguleri and Igbariam in order to identify areas with good aquifer potential zones and high transmissivity.

2. RELATED WORK

Ashhad and Quamrul (2019) investigated groundwater potential of an area in Delhi and concluded that the groundwater table at the pumping well lies at a depth of about 18.3m and goes to a depth of 47.6m. Hossain *et al.*, (2022) estimated hydraulic conductivity transmissivity and specific yield of aquifer in Barind area, Bangladesh using pumping test and concluded that Hydraulic Conductivity (K), Transmissivity (T) and Specific Yield (Sy) at Nachol were found as 17.22 to 55.35 m³/m²/day, 430.48 to 1383.69 m²/m/day and 4.03 to 5.17%, respectively, under different methods and Niamatpur area, the K, T and Sy were found as 37.58 to 103.90 m³/m²/day, 733.20 to 1027.28 m³/m/day, and 4.05 to 9.16%, respectively. Ismail *et al* (2008) estimated the transmissivity and storativity of aquifer using specific capacity of wells and concluded that it is possible to correct values of transmissibility and storativity by using the well – known Hantush modification (Hantush, 1961) of the Theis method or Boonstra method that consist of a matching procedure between the drawdown observed in the field and theoretical drawdown found from the analysis (Boonstra, 1992). Sylvia *et al* (2022) estimated groundwater potentials and transmissivity using Vertical Electrical Sounding and Dar Zarrouk parameters in Mapeo and Environs, North-Eastern Nigeria and concluded that the north and southeastern parts of the study are characterized by groundwater potential while moderate groundwater potentials are restricted to the central part of the study area.

In Nigeria, Olatunji *et al.*, (2016) investigated groundwater potential using electrical resistivity method in parts of Kwara State polytechnic Ilorin Nigeria and concluded that the quality and quantity of the borehole could not be predicted until after drilling have been done and testing pumping carried out. Oseji *et al.*, (2006) determined the groundwater potential in Obiaruku and environ, after interpretation of the resistivity curve came to a conclusion that the area has great groundwater potential revealing the lithologic succession as an extensive sandy unit between range of 20m and 136m. Ekwok *et al.*, (2020) made assessment of ground water potential using a geophysical data in cross river state and concluded that the OM and IME have thin to, moderate sediment thicknesses, while the CF is predominated by thick sedimentation (6217m). Ezeh and Ugwu (2010) carried out a geoelectrical sounding for estimating groundwater potential in Nsukka L.G.A. Enugu State, Nigeria and concluded that the presence of thick and highly prolific auriferous zone assures the area of adequate water resource. Emmanuel *et al* (2022) evaluated transmissibility and hydrogeological properties of aquifer system at Edem, Enugu state and concluded that the area has high distribution of permeability, hydraulic capillary radius, transmissivity, hydraulic conductivity and porosity with low distribution of surface area per unit volume and tortuosity was observed along the western and some at the eastern parts suggest high indices of groundwater transmissibility magnitude along these parts.

In Anambra State, Okafor (2020) investigated ground water potential of the Nanka sands around Nanka - Oko and its environment Anambra state, the result of the interpretation of the geo physical data shows that the area is characterized by a variable sub surface layering ranging from six layer to eight layers. Okeke (2012) investigated groundwater potential using direct geo electric method in a part of old Aguata and Anaocha local government area Anambra state and concluded that to harness potable water within the aquifer region, it was recommended that the borehole be drilled much beyond the depth range of 24.8m to 130.0m. Onuorah P. (2017) investigated groundwater occurrence using geo electric method in out-cha and environ Anambra state the result shows that the water saturation is more at the water table mound towards the north than the other areas. Chiwuko (2015) investigated ground water potential in Awka, Anambra state Nigeria using geo electric method and concluded that the aquifer are capable of yielding enough water that would serve the immediate environs. Delunzu *et al.*, (2018) made assessment of groundwater potential in Anambra state and got to a conclusion that the groundwater potential map could be useful for various purposes such as the development of sustainable scheme for groundwater in the area, the integration of geographical information system and data extracted from satellite images coupled with geophysical data and the geological knowledge of the area under investigation, could provide a powerful tool in groundwater investigation and groundwater potential zones map revealed that the plain areas are prospective zones in the catchment and can be helpful in better planning and management of ground resource. Onyekwelu *et al.*, (2021) investigated ground water potential of Ogidi and environs, Anambra state south- eastern Nigeria using geo electrical method and concluded that since the aquifer layer was encountered in all sounding location, this shows that the study area have good groundwater potential. Kenechukwu *et al.*, (2020) using geo electric technique for vulnerability and groundwater potential analysis of aquifer in Nnewi Anambra state Nigeria the result shows that the study area has stronger groundwater potential. Nzemeka *et al.*, (2023) investigated the groundwater potential and aquifer protective capacity at Aguleri and Nando, Anambra state and concluded that all the areas of study are areas of productive and sustainable borehole yield because of their high aquifer thicknesses.

3 MATERIALS

The basic equipment used for this geophysical survey is the ABEM SAS 1000 resistivity meter. The resistivity meter is equipped with a 12 volts battery, two current transmission cables on reels, two potential cables, four metal electrodes and a salt solution. Other auxiliary equipment for the survey include a Global Positioning System (GPS) for determining the resistivity survey locations and topography, geologic hammers for driving electrodes into the ground, two measuring tapes and cutlasses for clearing the traverses.

3.1 METHOD

The study involved the use of electrical resistivity method. The technique adopted was Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES). The sounding was used to characterize the various lithologic units and to determine the depth to water table. This method involves the supply of direct current or low-frequency alternating current into the ground through a pair of current electrodes (Fig 3) and the measurement of the resulting potential through another pair of electrode called potential electrodes (Obiabunmo *et al.*, 2014). Since the current is known and the potential can be

measured, an apparent resistivity can be calculated. For Schlumberger soundings, the apparent resistivity values (ρ_a) were plotted against half current electrode separation ($AB/2$) on a log-log graph and a smooth curve indicative of the vertical distribution in the subsurface was drawn for each of the soundings. Then, the sounding curves were interpreted to determine the true resistivities and thicknesses of the subsurface layers. Figure 2 is a schematic illustration of the data processing techniques applied to the raw ER data.

Fig 2: Flow diagram for Electrical Resistivity data processing Olawale and Olayinka (2012)

Fig 3: Schlumberger array (Nzemeka *et al.*, 2023)

A total of five soundings using Schlumberger array (fig 3) were carried out in the study area. The Vertical Electrical Sounding was used to determine the depth of water table and the subsurface geoelectric layers. The VES field data were processed using the Schlumberger automatic INTERPEX analysis software, which generates model curves using initial layer parameters. The Dar-Zarrouk parameters were obtained from the first order geoelectric parameters (layer resistivities and thicknesses). These include the total longitudinal unit conductance (S) and total transverse unit resistance (T). These secondary geoelectric parameters are particularly important

when they are used to describe a geoelectric section consisting of several layers (Zhody *et al.* 1974). For n layers, the total longitudinal unit conductance is

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{h_i}{\rho_i} \right) \quad 1$$

The total transverse unit resistance is given as

$$T = \sum_{i=1}^n \rho_i h_i \quad 2$$

where h_i is the thickness of the i th layer and ρ_i is the resistivity of the i th layer. Hydraulic conductivity and transmissivity was computed using equations 3 and 4. Hydraulic conductivity (K_h) values as given in Equation (3) (Heigold *et al.* 1979) were estimated from its relation with aquifer resistivity (R_w):

$$K_h = \frac{386.40}{R_w^{0.95283}} \quad 3$$

Hydraulic conductivity measures the opposition to the flow of water through a pore space. It helps in determining the renewal rate of groundwater, appraisal of groundwater yield and other hydraulic properties. It depends on the intrinsic permeability of the aquifer and its degree of saturation. Transmissivity (T_r) relating with hydraulic conductivity and thickness (h) was calculated using Equation (4) according to Todd (1980):

$$T_r = K_h h \quad 4$$

It controls groundwater flow, provides a general idea on the water-producing efficiency of an aquifer and describes the capacity of the aquifer to transmit groundwater wholly in its entire saturated thickness (Omeje *et al.* 2021). Using modified Freeze & Cherry 1979 classification, the results of transmissivity was used to classify areas into very good, good, moderately good, low/fairly good and poor aquifer transmissivity as shown in Table 1. The lithology was inferred to the layers from the correlation between the one of the borehole drilled in the study area and geology of the study area (Ugwu and Ezeh, 2012).

Table 1: Classification of Aquifer Based on Transmissivity (Modified after Freeze & Cherry 1979)

Transmissivity Value (m ² /day)	Aquifer Rating
T > 500	Very Good
150 < T < 500	Good
50 < T < 150	Moderately Good
10 < T < 50	Low/fairly Good
1 < T < 10	Poor

The ABEM SAS 1000 resistivity meter and the 12 volts battery were placed in the centre of the layout. The two inner electrodes are the potential electrodes while the two outer electrodes are the

current electrodes as shown in fig. 3. Four cables were connected to the resistivity meter at the centre of the cable spread and the electrodes were connected at the other end of cables. Current is passed between electrodes A and B and monitored by the potential electrodes M and N. As the distance between A and B is increased, deeper horizon have more effect on the potential between M and N. Also when sounding with a Schlumberger array, as distance between the current electrodes are increased, the distance between the current and potential electrodes at the center of the array is also increased. It is this increase between the current and potential electrodes at the center of the array that actually matters in depth probing. The reasonable distance between M and N should be equal or less than one-fifth of the distance between A and B at the beginning. The ratio goes up to one – tenth or one – fifteenth depending on the signal strength. The electrode configuration having a maximum current electrode spread of 200 m was used with a maximum of 100 m on both sides. The current electrode spacing begins with a distance equal to 2 m and extends up to 100 m while the potential electrode spacing begins with a distance of 0.5m and extends up to 20m. The $\frac{AB}{2}$ or half current electrode spacing was increased to a maximum of 100 meters. In most cases $\frac{MN}{2}$ or half potential electrode spacing were overlapping two readings. This means that the potential electrodes were moved only when the potential drops or becomes too small to measure with sufficient accuracy. For the survey, it was not necessary to increase the $\frac{MN}{2}$ distance until the distance $\frac{AB}{2}$ was increased to 9, 75 and 100 meters. At this point, $\frac{\Delta V}{I}$ was measured for both the old and new value of $\frac{MN}{2}$. This procedure permits the detection of near surface inhomogeneities.

4 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Qualitative interpretation of the profiles and depth sounding curves were carried out based on distinctive geoelectric parameters of the layers represented by the four types of auxiliary curve (A, H, K and Q). VES 1 and 3 are type QH curves while VES 2, 4 and 5 are type A, HH and QHK type of curves respectively (Fig 4 - 8). VES 1, 2 and 3 have four geoelectric layers while VES 4 and 5 have five (5) and six (6) geoelectric layers (Table 2). A summary of qualitative interpretation of VES curves is shown in Table 2 while Table 3 shows a summary of the quantitative interpretation results of the VES.

TABLE 2: SUMMARY OF QUALITATIVE INTERPRETATION OF VES CURVES

VES	COORDINATE	CURVE TYPE	RESISTIVITY PROFILE	NUMBER OF LAYERS
1	06 ⁰ 17' 14.2"N 006 ⁰ 51' 35.0" E	QH	$\rho_1 > \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4$	4
2	06 ⁰ 23' 50.3"N 006 ⁰ 57' 07.5" E	A	$\rho_1 < \rho_2 < \rho_3 < \rho_4$	4

3	N 06°17'14.2"N E 006°51'35.0"E	QH	$\rho_1 > \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4$	4
4	N 06°19'12.2"N E 006°54'10.0"E	HH	$\rho_1 > \rho_2 < \rho_3 > \rho_4 < \rho_5$	5
5	N 06°20'08.7"N E 006°54'05.6"E	QHK	$\rho_1 > \rho_2 > \rho_3 > \rho_4 < \rho_5 > \rho_6$	6

Fig 4: Interpretation result of VES 1 data
2 data

Fig 5: Interpretation result of VES

Fig 6: Interpretation result of VES 3 data
data

Fig 7: Interpretation result of VES 4

Fig 8: Interpretation result of VES 5 data

TABLE 3: SUMMARY OF VES INTERPRETATION RESULTS

VES	layers	Resistivity (Ωm)	Thickness (m)	Depth (m)	Lithology	Longitudinal conductance S (mhos)	Transverse resistance (Ω)	Hydraulic conductivity	Cal. Transmissivity (m^2/d)	Aquifer Transmissivity Rating
1	1	89.80	20	20	Dry sand	0.223	1796	0.058	1.16	
	2	16.44	10	30	Shale	0.608	164.4	28.592	285.92	
	3	2.96	20	50	Water saturated sand	6.757	59.2	140.84	2816.80	Very Good
	4	4.70	50	100	Shale	10.638	235	91.619	4580.95	
2	1	22.22	10	10	Shale	0.450	222.2	0.146	1.460	
	2	25.84	20	30	Silty shale	0.774	516.8	0.292	5.840	
	3	68.47	30	60	Water saturated sand	0.438	2054.1	0.0146	0.438	Poor
	4	237.76	40	100	Sand	0.168	9506	0.584	23.36	
3	1	31.655	5.33	5.33	Red Earth	0.168	168.72	15.395	82.055	

	2	23.0025	14.67	20.00	Shaly Sand	0.638	337.45	20.736	304.197	
	3	19.6017	60.00	80.00	Shale	3.061	1176.10	24.074	1444.440	
	4	300.557	53.33	133.33	Water Saturated Sand	0.177	16028.70	1.886	100.580	Moderately Good
4	1	433.35	5.33	5.33	Red Earth	0.0122	2309.76	1.341	7.148	
	2	267.024	34.67	40.00	Shaly Sand	0.1298	9257.72	2.106	73.015	
	3	853.375	40.00	80.00	Sandstone	0.0469	34135	0.713	28.520	
	4	605.652	53.33	133.33	Water Saturated Sand	0.0881	32299.42	0.981	52.317	Moderately Good
	5	1850.803	40.00	173.33	Shaly Sand	0.0216	74032.12	0.346	13.840	
5	1	179.76	4.00	4.00	Red Earth	0.0223	719.04	3.046	12.184	
	2	66.45	6.00	10.00	Shaly Sand	0.0903	398.70	7.708	46.248	
	3	9.7075	60.00	70.00	Shale	6.1808	582.45	46.370	2782.200	
	4	5.71	30.00	100.00	Water Saturated Sand	5.2539	171.30	76.072	2282.160	Very Good
	5	6.9667	60.00	160.00	Water Saturated Sand	8.6124	418.00	63.188	3791.280	
	6	5.9725	40.00	200.00	Shaly Sand	6.6974	238.90	72.948	2917.92	

A correlation between the lithologic logs of boreholes of Igboezunu town square Aguleri, Proposed fire service, Onitsha, Igbariam Inland town and Abube Agu Nando drilled 40m, 60m and 50m away from the study areas (VES 1 – 5) respectively obtained from the State Ministry of Water Resources and the interpretation results of VES 1 – 3 as shown in Table 3 shows the occurrence of four (4) lithologic layers while VES 4 and 5 shows five (5) and six (6) lithologic layers namely: dry sand, shale, water saturated sand, silty shale, sand, red earth, sandstone and shaly sand as shown in Table 3. The first layers has resistivity values ranging from 89.80 – 433.35 Ω m, inferred to be dry sand, shale and red earth respectively with thickness values ranging from 4 – 20m. The second layers inferred as shale, silty shale and shaly sand with resistivity values ranging from 16.44 – 267.024 Ω m and thickness values ranging from 10 – 20m. The resistivity values of the third and fourth layers ranges from 2.96 – 853.375 Ω m with thickness values ranging from 20 – 60m. The aquifer layers are water saturated sand which is located at the third layer in VES 1 and 2; fourth layer in VES 3 – 5, it is at these layers that the aquifer are located in agreement with the result of Oyeku and Eludoyin (2010), Nzemeka *et al.*, 2023 and Uma (2003). The third layer for VES 3 – 5 inferred as shale and sandstone respectively. Their resistivity values ranges from 9.7075 – 853.375 Ω m with thickness values ranging from 40 – 60m. The fifth and sixth layers in VES 5 and 6 are inferred as shaly sand with resistivity values ranging from 5.9725 - 1850.803 Ω m and thickness values ranges from 40 – 60m. Fig. The aquifer transmissivity was determined by calculating for hydraulic conductivity and multiplying with the thickness of the aquifer layer in the VES 1 – 5. The aquifer transmissivity values obtained was 2816.80, 0.438, 100.580, 52.317 and 2282.160m²/day which indicates a very good, poor, moderately good aquifer transmissivities respectively. Groundwater potential zones were determined based on transmissivity values in accordance with the result of Sylvia *et al* (2022) and Emmanuel *et al* (2022). VES 1 and 5 are seen to be areas with good groundwater potentials because of their high transmissivity values as such are good area to site boreholes.

5. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

In this study, the groundwater potential and transmissivity of the aquifer unit in Nando, Aguleri and Igbariam, Anambra State was undertaken using five (5) Vertical Electrical Soundings. The results showed a very good, poor, moderately good aquifer transmissivities respectively. Groundwater potential zones were determined based on transmissivity values. VES 1 and 5 are seen to be areas with good groundwater potentials because of their high transmissivity values as such are good area for good boreholes yield. The rest of the study areas shows poor and moderately good aquifer transmissivities. Thus the information obtained from this study can serve as a baseline data for pre-drilling estimation of the yield of any prospective borehole in the areas.

6. LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER STUDIES

Just as this study limits at finding the areas with good aquifer potential and transmissivities, I recommend that more geophysical surveys be conducted at Aguleri and Igbariam villages in other to ascertain areas where good groundwater potential could be harnessed and the contamination infiltration rate of the research areas.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

My profound gratitude goes to God who made it possible for me to be alive and achieve this research work. A very big thank you to every member of my family especially my wife Mrs. C.R. Olisah and my lovely parents Chief and Mrs. N.E. Olisah; Pastor and Prof. T.N. Obiekezie for their financial assistance and care. I also wish to acknowledge my friends who helped me in one way or the other to make this research work a success. May the Almighty God bless you all.

AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Authors have declared this paper is solely written by us and there no duplication of any sort.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

Olisah Nzemeka C. is a geophysicist who has carried out various research work especially on groundwater potential and vulnerability in Enugu and Anambra State. I contributed to the analysis by collecting data at these towns and creating the map and figures depicting terrain, surface water and groundwater.

Ogbogu Bonaventure. is a student of geophysics who carried out all the interpretation and analyzing existing water resources data.

Obiekezie T.N. is a professor and an atmospheric geophysicist who has mentor various students in research work in Atmospheric geophysics in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. She contributed in the equipment used in acquiring the data and also in data interpretation and processing.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: The data utilized for this study will be made available upon reasonable request.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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